

EXPLORATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF LABOR EDUCATION EVALUATION SYSTEM IN EXPERIMENTAL AND PRACTICAL TRAINING COURSES

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ABSTRACT

The evaluation of the impact of labor education has emerged as a key area for educational reform, which has improved the evaluation standards and frameworks for labor education and curriculum implementation. However, there are still issues with the current labor education implementation quality evaluation system in experimental and practical training courses, including the use of straightforward evaluation methods and single means as well as the inability to provide feedback on the evaluation results to the design and implementation of the curriculum. This paper analyzes and summarizes the implementation objectives, implementation processes, and evaluation results of the implementation of the experimental and practical training courses based on their implementation in local colleges and universities. On this foundation, the LCPI course evaluation model is investigated and developed with the goal of offering an operational course evaluation model for the implementation of quality evaluation of labor education in nearby colleges and universities. This model integrates course positioning analysis, content setting, process evaluation, and implementation feedback.

Keywords: local universities; experimental training; labor education; evaluation system; LCPI Model

INTRODUCTION

The Opinions on Comprehensively Strengthening Labor Education in Primary and Secondary Schools in the New Era (hereinafter referred to as the "Opinions") and the Overall Plan for Deepening the Reform of Educational Evaluation in the New Era (hereinafter referred to as the "Plan") were released by the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and the State Council, respectively, in 2020. The goals of the "plan" and the "opinions" are to execute and implement the National Education Conference's ethos fully. It identifies the path for modernizing Chinese education and creating a strong national education system, and it raises the necessity for reforming labor education evaluation in colleges and universities in the new era by elevating labor education to the pinnacle of national development in education. In order to realize the organic integration of the two, have the greatest impact on improving the caliber of talent

training, and truly achieve comprehensive education, colleges and universities should encourage the effective integration of labor education into professional education by assisting students in developing sound labor values, reforming the curriculum system, enhancing the teaching staff, and implementing school-enterprise dual education (Song, 2022). We can create a labor education system that keeps up with the times by continuously examining and innovating labor education and implementation methods, which will then enable the labor course to take on the role of the new era's educational goal. (Cao et al., 2022). For students to understand the meaning and true meaning of labor, as well as to develop a new era of hard-working, diligent, thrifty, and pioneering spirit, labor education requires the cooperation and participation of the government, colleges and universities, families, and students (Dong & Li, 2022). College labor education in the new era is a crucial component of the higher education personnel training system that adheres to the new era's labor development trend by methodically educating college students on labor philosophy, labor skills, and labor practice (Qu & Liu, 2019). Experimental and practical training courses are the main source of the portion of the higher education personnel training system that involves skill development and practical training. As a result, the investigation and creation of a labor education implementation quality evaluation system in experimental and practical training courses are of utmost importance for the development of the particular shape and impact of labor education's presentation.

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

The major goal of this study is to gather, arrange, and analyze the literature on labor education in order to identify the research topic's turning point. This study focuses on analyzing the deficiencies and challenges of the current labor education implementation quality evaluation system for experimental and practical training courses, as well as the reasons behind such challenges. This analysis was made possible by thorough research on the quality evaluation system of labor education and the implementation of experimental and practical training courses that have been conducted. In order to more effectively improve the impact and promote experimental training courses in labor education, this research explores and develops a novel curriculum evaluation model.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The goal of this study is to identify the flaws and challenges in the current system for evaluating experimental and practical training courses and to investigate a new model for curriculum evaluation to enhance the impact of labor education implementation. The following three concerns will thus be the main focus of this investigation:

RQ1. What are the existing labor education evaluation system's flaws and challenges for experimental and practical training courses?

RQ2. How should the impact of the work-related education provided in the experimental practical training course be assessed?

RQ3. How can teachers enhance the contribution of occupational education to the creation of experimental and practical training programs?

LITERATURE REVIEW

IMPORTANCE OF LABOR EDUCATION

A crucial component of fostering college students' overall moral, intellectual, physical, American, and labor development in the context of the new era is labor education (Yang, 2022). In addition to passing down and expanding the Marxist notion of labor, we should encourage the development of the new generation's personal skills and labor literacy, and we should emphasize the beneficial effects of labor education on student development (Jia, 2021). For college students to achieve self-realization, self-development, and self-perfection, as well as the objective of moral education, labor education is an effective vehicle that combines theoretical and practical education (Feng & Liu, 2019). The ultimate aim of labor education is to instill labor ideals in college students for the modern world. Through classroom instruction and hands-on practice, teachers should foster the work ethic and work habits of college students in order to increase their labor productivity (Sun, 2023). Labor education is a crucial component of the essential work of fostering morals and educating people, as well as an important method of instructing and guiding pupils. It helps students develop the right perspective on life, values, and the wider world.

THE INFLUENCE OF PRACTICAL COURSES ON LABOR EDUCATION

In labor education, theoretical teaching and classroom instruction are crucial links, but practical courses are also crucial for advancing labor education, and the effectiveness of theoretical learning must be verified in practice (Zeng, 2023). The practical guidelines for labor education place a strong emphasis on the need for schools and teachers to give students more varied practice opportunities, develop their practical skills, and fully utilize practical courses in order to advance labor education and maximize its impact (Gao, 2023). It is important to emphasize the promotion of practical courses in labor education, maintain the "theory + practice" approach, and realize the "integration of science and practice" education model as part of the labor education implementation process (Wang, 2021).

EVALUATION SYSTEM OF LABOR EDUCATION

The development of a multi-dimensional labor education curriculum system, the design of teaching materials and implementation strategies around the curriculum system, the establishment of assessment indicators in accordance with educational objectives, and the formation of a sound labor education system through evaluation, feedback, and continuous improvement are all crucial (Jing, 2022). An essential component of the performance of labor education is the curriculum evaluation system. In addition to serving as the labor curriculum's compass, it also serves as a quality control checkpoint and a catalyst for curriculum improvement (Zheng, 2023). The development and execution of labor education curricula require the use of a rational and scientific curriculum evaluation index system, which is also the key to enabling schools and teachers to successfully modify and enhance the curriculum (Fang & Tian, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Evaluation of the curriculum is crucial to the success of curriculum change and implementation. The American academic Taylor (2014) proposes a well-known curriculum goal model because he believes that curriculum evaluation is the benchmark to determine whether the curriculum goals have been attained. According to Kronbach (1989), formative evaluation is more beneficial when it is followed by ideas for improvement. According to Stavelbeam (1989), the main goal of evaluation is to improve rather than to prove something. As a result, he proposed a comprehensive evaluation model for classroom teaching evaluation—a CIPP evaluation model integrating thorough background evaluation, input evaluation, process evaluation, and outcome evaluation.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study first adopted the literature research method, and it consulted a large number of studies on the form of labor education, teaching process, and effect evaluation on "CNKI" in order to effectively improve the effectiveness of labor education in experimental and practical training courses for science and engineering majors in local applied colleges and universities in central and western China. In order to identify research concerns, this study summarizes the shortcomings of labor education in the creation of experimental and practical training programs. Next, using the author's teaching experience, the CIPP comprehensive evaluation model, and the descriptive research method, I searched "Google Academic" for research on curriculum evaluation. Simulation is used to construct a new curriculum evaluation system that is appropriate for the demands of the modern classroom, fulfills students' real needs, and can significantly enhance the learning experience (Stavelbeam, 1989). Qualitative research will be employed in the author's next study to confirm the reasonableness of the curriculum evaluation model created. Fifty second-year environmental science and engineering majors from an applied university in central and western China were chosen as the research subjects during the program verification procedure. Semi-structured interviews were carried out as part of a six-month course teaching research project to get their opinions, experiences, and recommendations on the new course evaluation system. Ultimately, the gathered data is interpreted, coded, and subjected to thematic analysis.

FINDINGS

The LCPI curriculum evaluation system is based on the implementation of labor education in experimental and practical training courses, and the curriculum location analysis is built as a guide to comprehensively strengthen the cognition of labor education in experimental and practical training courses to effectively solve the difficulties existing in the quality evaluation system of that implementation, the specific implementation path is shown in Figure 1. To

effectively integrate labor education and curriculum teaching, it is important to appropriately communicate to students the value orientation of labor education and conduct a more thorough analysis of the aim of curriculum teaching. In order to achieve Content Settings, the labor education requirements should be combined with the new requirements of the new era to innovate the labor education content, implement the labor education content with The Times, strengthen the curriculum content, and improve the effectiveness of the labor education in experimental and practical training courses; Process evaluation is used to implement labor education evaluation methods in experimental and practical training courses in a variety of ways, and efficient process evaluation methods are used to tangibly show the teaching effect and identify teaching flaws and areas that urgently require improvement. The teaching impact directly influences the accurate analysis of curriculum positioning and the prompt updating of curriculum content setting, forming a continuous cycle mechanism of labor education in curriculum "positioning analysis, content setting, process evaluation, and implementation feedback" in order to build a systematic feedback system for the purpose of curriculum implementation feedback. It thus establishes the framework for the natural alignment of experimental and practical training programs with occupational education.

Figure1. LCPI Curriculum Evaluation System

DISCUSSION

EXAMINATION OF HOW LABOR EDUCATION IS POSITIONED IN HANDS-ON AND EXPERIMENTAL TRAINING PROGRAMS

The experimental training course's major goal is to put theoretical knowledge into practice and further demonstrate the validity of the theory by doing so. The practice also serves as a transitional connection between subjectivity and objectivity, the only means of bridging theory and practice and a crucial component in the transformation and unification of the subjective and objective worlds (Li et al., 2019). A sizeable percentage of the curriculum is taken up by the experimental and practical training programs for scientific and engineering majors, which is a crucial component of the professional development of these students. The curriculum itself should clearly state that practice is the key to experimental and practical training and that it is the foundation of labor education practice, accurately acknowledge the placement of labor education within the experimental and practical training course, and fully acknowledge that the experimental and practical training course is an important means of carrying out labor education. Therefore, there needs to be agreement on and continued focus on the requirement of labor education in the formulation of experimental and practical training curriculum objectives. It is important to check whether teachers clearly mark the purpose, content, and implementation method of labor education in the preparation of teaching syllabuses and the implementation of teaching weekly calendars, as well as whether labor education is combined with the ideological and political reform of curriculum in the evaluation system of the experimental and practical training curriculum. Teachers should clearly analyze the curriculum construction of labor education in syllabus preparation, teaching design, teaching plan writing, teaching implementation, teaching evaluation, and teaching feedback. They should also accurately grasp the specific performance of the core elements of labor education in the entire process of curriculum implementation.

SETTING THE CONTENT OF COURSES IN EXPERIMENTAL AND PRACTICAL TRAINING

The theoretical curriculum for labor education focuses more on the study and research of labor education than it does on actual work performance, making it impossible to accurately and effectively assess the impact of labor education. The experimental practical training course emphasizes teaching students experimental skills and verifying their theoretical understanding. As far as the curriculum content goes, this technique allows for a more thorough and logical organization of the content for labor education. The first is to determine whether the curriculum content setting is aligned with the national education development strategy and whether it includes educational guidance and concept instillation for the training of young scientific and technological talents, craftsmen of great countries, excellent engineers, and high-level skilled talents. To achieve the goal of teaching students to respect and be proud of labor, the context of this curriculum component is crucial for the development of students' labor consciousness and labor concepts. It can also play a significant role in promoting the formation of students' correct labor cognition. The second is to assess if the aim and core of labor education are included in the curriculum's content and to determine whether it covers labor attitude, labor aptitude, labor habit, and labor spirit (Gong et al., 2020). The labor curriculum content should be put up in accordance with the standards, and the curriculum content should have clear

investigation points in the curriculum content establishment. The creation of curriculum material should reflect the purpose of labor education.

EVALUATION OF THE LABOR EDUCATION PROCESS IN COURSES INCLUDING EXPERIMENTATION AND PRACTICE

Practical teaching can directly represent the presentation format of a labor education course, and teaching practice is the primary format of an experimental and practical training course. Students can develop a knowledge formation system of "practice-know-re-practice-re-understanding" through the development and improvement of practical competence in experimental and practical training courses. Therefore, a crucial component of curriculum development, implementation, reflection, and improvement is the multi-process evaluation of labor education in experimental and practical training courses. It is advisable to weaken the conventional assessment method, which combines the preview report, experiment operation, and experiment report, and to strengthen the expression form and evaluation framework for labor education in experimental training programs. First, during pre-training for the experiment, did students reference background information, production applications, and technological implementation paths connected to the experiment? The ability of students to independently apply new knowledge is the focus of the evaluation. The second is whether or not the pupils exhibit attentive attention and constructive thinking in the experimental training class, and the test variable is whether or not they respect labor. The third is whether or not students have an awareness of safety, cooperation, and accountability during experimentation and practical instruction. The pupils' ability to work safely, cooperatively, conscientiously, and responsibly is the test point. Fourth, check to see if the experimental training report included information about labor consciousness and labor cooperation as well as a summary of the students' work during the writing process.

COMMENTS ON HOW LABOR EDUCATION IS BEING IMPLEMENTED IN EXPERIMENTAL AND PRACTICAL TRAINING COURSES

The experimental and practical training course plays a significant role in enhancing the efficacy of labor education as a means of enhancing the professional practice capacity of college students. The objectives for instruction, the tasks for instruction, and the creation of curricula are continuously enhanced through the evaluation findings of the labor education process of the experimental and practical training courses. First, teachers should promptly change the content of the course introduction by adding the spirit of craftsmen in great countries and cases of superb engineers based on the evaluation results of students' own labor ability in the preliminary part of experimentation and practical training. Second, in order to increase student appreciation for teachers' work in the classroom, we need to improve teachers' political and ideological views, as well as their competency in the classroom. Third, constantly modify the experimental and practical training lesson plan, placing emphasis on the addition and improvement of aspects such as labor safety, cooperation, consciousness, and responsibility. This is done based on the evaluation results of the students' experimental and practical training processes. This section of the curriculum should be the focal point of the entire evaluation system because it can significantly aid students in growing their sense of responsibility, cooperation, and

safety in the workplace. Fourthly, it is possible to comprehend the students' understanding of work while learning professional information and abilities by merging the evaluation findings in the students' summary report. Teachers can timely reflect on their lessons thanks to feedback from evaluation outcomes, which helps to maintain a high standard of instruction.

CONCLUSION

A significant accomplishment of the educational system in the modern age is the thorough development of labor education, which has contributed significantly to the advancement of workers and societal respect. The aim of education in colleges and universities needs to be broad; the mode of education ought to keep up with the times, and the outcome of education ought to keep up with the demands of society. Local colleges and universities play a major role in training applied abilities; therefore, vocational education must permeate the entire curriculum. The experimental and practical training programs can give students the tools they need to work, including the development of work ethics, work aptitude, and work skills. The goal of this research is to develop an assessment framework appropriate for use in labor education programs. The LCPI course evaluation model is developed in this study using the work of other researchers. The goal is to support regional universities and applied schools in enhancing the impact of labor education through the implementation of hands-on, experimental training programs.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study examined the labor education evaluation system in the modern era and created a new evaluation system that served as a guide for improving the impact of labor education in local colleges and universities' experimental and practical training courses. It also sorted out the shortcomings and challenges of labor education evaluation in the implementation of experimental and practical training courses in these institutions.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Because of the short study period, only CNKI provided a sufficient reading volume and research of the necessary literature, which may have resulted in an inadequate examination of certain issues. Furthermore, there is insufficient effective data support, and the LCPI course assessment system is still in the application stage of implementation.

FURTHER RESEARCH

The author will conduct practice at local application-oriented colleges and universities in western China in accordance with the LCPI curriculum evaluation system developed in this study. The practice will use questionnaires and interviews to conduct empirical research with a focus on evaluating the application of labor education in the experimental practical training course.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

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